

VISCOELASTIC BEHAVIOUR OF SINGLE HEMP FIBRE UNDER CONSTANT AND CYCLIC HUMIDITY ENVIRONMENT - EXPERIMENT AND MODELLING.

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Keywords: Hemp fibres, Viscoelasticity, Tensile creep

ABSTRACT

Natural fibres derived from annual plants are attractive candidates to reinforce organic matrix in high performance composite applications. This use requires an accurate understanding of their mechanical properties and the development of efficient models. In the last years, many efforts were focused on the characterisation of the tensile properties of bast fibres under quasi-static loading. In contrast, the time-dependent behaviour has almost not been examined. However, considering the polymeric composition of their wall, plant fibres can exhibit to greater or lesser extent viscoelastic behaviour. This point is of great importance in view of their integration in composite materials. Effectively, contrary to glass or carbon fibres reinforced plastics, the time-dependent behaviour of natural fibres reinforced plastics could arise both from the matrix and the fibres.

The aim of this study is to investigate and model the time-dependent tensile behaviour of single hemp fibres. This work proposes an experimental approach, using creep tests and Dynamic Mechanical Analysis under constant and cyclic humidity environment. A 3D anisotropic viscoelastic model based on a spectral distribution of elementary mechanisms is proposed to describe the time-delayed response of these fibres.

Hemp fibres are shown to exhibit both instantaneous deformation and delayed, time-dependent deformation when tensile loaded. Under constant environment, three types of creep behaviour are observed. Our results show that an inverse Gaussian spectral model with truncation associated to a reliable parameters identification strategy is able to describe accurately the 3 types of creep behaviour. The primary and secondary creep rates are also shown to be highly influenced by the moisture level and moisture cycling.

Finally, the anisotropic viscoelastic constitutive law identified using creep tests is used to simulate the quasi-static tensile behaviour of such fibres. It demonstrated that the experimentally observed nonlinear tensile behaviour can be partly attributed to viscoelastic mechanisms.

1 INTRODUCTION

To the best of the authors' knowledge, only few results have been collected on the creep behaviour of plant fibre composites (1-5) and no information on the creep behaviour of cellulosic fibres derived from annual plants, such as hemp and flax, are available in literature. A few results were found on bamboo fibres (6). Yu et al. (6) showed the time dependency on the creep deformation of such fibres. They also emphasize the effect of moisture content on the creep behaviour. A limited number of papers is also related to the creep behaviour of single wood fibres (7-12). Their creep behaviour has been studied in the context of their use in the paper and packaging applications. Elementary wood fibre has been shown to exhibit both instantaneous elastic deformation and delayed, time-dependent deformation when subjected to an externally applied load, and a permanent strain when the load is removed (7-9). Wood fibres also exhibit increase in creep compliance with increasing moisture content. Several authors also observed much greater creep in cyclic humidity conditions than in a constant environment at the high-humidity extreme (10-12). This accelerated creep phenomenon, induced by the sorption and desorption of water in the fibre wall, is known as mechanosorptive (MCS)

effect. So the time-dependent behaviour of wood fibres not only depends on the temperature, the loading history, the moisture content but also on moisture content history as well as moisture variations. These parameters can interact and produce coupling effects (13). The existence of MCS creep for single wood fibres is widely debated in the scientific community since negative results have been published (7-10).

So, the aim of this study is to investigate the time-moisture dependent tensile behaviour of hemp fibres.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Plant material

Non-retted hemp fibres (*Cannabis sativa* L., cultivars 'Fedora 17') tested in this paper, were supplied by the LCDA (La Chanvrière De l'Aube) company in France. They were delivered in a jumbled state after an extraction made using a mechanical process. Bundles of fibres were then washed in water for 72 h at 30°C in order to facilitate the extraction of elementary fibres. Single fibres were manually extracted and glued on thin paper supports. The isolated single fibres were firstly examined using polarised light microscopy (Nikon Eclipse LV 150), to determine their outer diameters. The average diameter of each fibre was computed by taking ten measurements along its length.

2.2 Determination of the viscoelastic properties of single plant fibres

The time dependent characteristics can be measured by static tests or by Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA). In this study, a Dynamic Mechanical Analyser (DMA Bose Electroforce 3230) was used to perform both tensile static (creep/recovery and relaxation/blotting-out tests) and harmonic tests. In most of the experiments, creep/recovery tests were preferred to relaxation/blotting-out tests considering the problem of fibre buckling that can be encountered during blotting-out tests. The paper frame supporting each elementary fibre was clamped onto the testing machine. Thereafter the fibre was conditioned to the required relative humidity up to the fibre reached moisture equilibrium. The time to reach the equilibrium was determined previously using isotherms of vapour water desorption/sorption. The paper frame was cut before the beginning of each test.

Several experiments were performed on carbon fibres to ensure that the glue and the extremity of the paper frame do not contribute to any creep or time-delayed behaviour.

The clamping length was 10 mm. The applied force was measured with a load sensor of 2 N with a resolution of about 1 mN, and the displacement was measured using a LVDT with a resolution of about 0.5 μm . To achieve the control of the environment around the natural fibres the machine was implemented with a relative humidity (RH) generator. The RH is controlled inside the sample chamber using a temperature and a humidity sensors placed inside the chamber, a few centimetres from the sample. The typical operating range is 10% to 90% at room temperature.

Fibres were subjected to static and harmonic loads. The sample elongation was measured and the strain calculated as the elongation divided by the initial fibre length. Tests were performed on fibres with an average external diameter of approximately 30 μm . The effective cross-section was determined using this mean external diameter assuming the fibre to be perfectly cylindrical and neglecting the lumen area. The stress was calculated using the applied force and the evaluated initial cross-section mean value of the fibre. The variation of the cross-section during tensile loading was neglected.

3 VISCOELASTIC MODEL

3.1 Model

In this work, the anisotropic viscoelastic model proposed by Boubakar et al. (14) and already applied to hemp fibres (15) was used. Assuming that the local state of the material is completely defined by the elastic strain tensor $\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e$ and a set of second order tensors $\underline{\underline{\xi}}_i$ ($i \in \mathbb{N}$) corresponding to N elementary

mechanisms of viscoelastic flow, the state law leads to the following instantaneous constitutive equation :

$$\underline{\dot{\underline{\varepsilon}}} - \underline{\dot{\underline{\varepsilon}}}^{ve}(\underline{\xi}_i; \underline{\sigma}) = \underline{\underline{S}}\underline{\dot{\underline{\sigma}}}, \quad (1)$$

where $\underline{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy true stress tensor, $\underline{\underline{S}}$ the elastic compliance tensor corresponding to a transverse isotropic behaviour with respect to the cellulose microfibrils direction, $\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^{ve}$ the viscoelastic strain tensor and $\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}$ the total strain tensor such as $\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}} = \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e + \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^{ve}$.

Following (14), the viscoelastic flow rule is given by:

$$\underline{\dot{\underline{\varepsilon}}}^{ve} = \sum_{i=1}^N \underline{\dot{\underline{\xi}}}_i = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\tau_i} \left(\mu_i \underline{\underline{S}}^{ve} \underline{\sigma} - \underline{\xi}_i \right), \quad (2)$$

where $\underline{\underline{S}}^{ve}$ is a viscoelastic compliance tensor whom general form is derived by considering an isotropic transverse behaviour with respect to the microfibrils direction, which is assumed to be purely elastic:

$$\underline{\underline{S}}^{ve} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\beta_T}{E_T} & -\frac{\beta_{TT\nu_{TT}}}{E_T} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{\beta_{TT\nu_{TT}}}{E_T} & \frac{\beta_T}{E_T} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\beta_{LT}}{G_T} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\beta_{LT}}{G_T} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\beta^*}{G_{TT}} \end{pmatrix}; \frac{\beta^*}{G_{TT}} = 2 \left(\frac{\beta_T}{E_T} + \frac{\beta_{TT\nu_{TT}}}{E_T} \right) \quad (3)$$

Such a tensor requires, in addition to the classical elastic parameters, the identification of three new parameters ($\beta_T, \beta_{TT}, \beta_{LT}$) related to the viscoelastic behaviour.

As given in equation 2, the effect of each elementary viscous mechanisms (i) is differentiated using weighting coefficients μ_i . The coefficients μ_i and the corresponding release time τ_i can be obtained from different types of relaxation times spectrum layout. Several spectral models were tested in a previous study (16). It was shown that an inverse Gaussian (IG) distributions (Fig.1) is able to balance two main release times (and by this way to fit all the experimentally observed creep behaviours) but with a single spectral distribution, thereby limiting the number of shape parameters. The weighting function is normalized by the following relation:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \mu_i = 1 \quad (4)$$

where N represents the number of mechanisms of the viscoelastic model. In this study, N is not considered as a parameter and is fixed to 31. This value was empirically fixed to ensure enough accuracy.

The inverse Gaussian spectrum is described by the mean τ_1 and the standard-deviation σ_d . Hence, μ_i is given by equation (5).

$$\mu_i = \frac{\exp\left(\frac{1}{2\sigma_d^2}(\ln\tau_i - \ln\tau_1)^2\right)}{\sum_{i=1}^N \exp\left(\frac{1}{2\sigma_d^2}(\ln\tau_i - \ln\tau_1)^2\right)} \quad (5)$$

To complete the model, two parameters are added in order to truncate the distributions differently at left and right sides. These parameters n_{min} and n_{max} are used to define the τ_{min} and τ_{max} boundaries of the distribution. Both n_{min} and n_{max} are real number comprised between 0 and 1. The N mechanisms are equally distributed between these two boundaries.

Figure 1: Inverse spectral Gaussian model.

3.2 Parameter identification

Two scalar independent creep functions have to be experimentally determined to characterize anisotropic time-dependent behaviour of hemp fibres. Laborious experimentations work has to be performed to determine these functions, in particular to determine the transverse creep function. In this study, we are only working with the experimentally determined axial creep function. The theoretical axial viscoelastic compliance $J_{ZZ}(t)$ is expressed as follows:

$$J_{ZZ}(t) = \frac{\varepsilon_{ZZ}^{ve}(t)}{\sigma_0} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{31} \mu_i S_{ZZ} (1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_i}})}{\sigma_0} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where } S_{ZZ} = \frac{\beta_T}{E_T} \cos^4(\psi) + \frac{\beta_{LT}}{G_{LT}} \cos^2(\psi) \sin^2(\psi) \quad (7)$$

ψ is the supplementary angle of the cellulose Microfibrils Angle (MFA) and σ_0 the constant axial stress.

On the basis of the axial viscoelastic compliance, only S_{zz} parameter can be identified (Eq. 6). This parameter was identified using the aforementioned model and a hybrid optimisation algorithm. In order to avoid convergence towards local optima in the case of multimodal test functions, the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm was combined with a heuristic method based on a genetic algorithm. This hybrid algorithm is described in (17, 18), and involves minimisation of the objective function f (Eq. 9).

$$f = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{J_{ZZ_{exp}}^k - J_{ZZ_{mod}}^k}{\max(J_{ZZ_{exp}}^k)} \right)^2}}{2n} \quad (9)$$

where $J_{ZZ_{exp}}^k$ is the k^{th} value of the experimental compliance data, $J_{ZZ_{mod}}^k$ is the k^{th} computed value using the aforementioned model, and n is the number of elements in the dataset.

To perform the identification of the parameters, the inverse identification strategy for restricted or redundant data proposed in (19) is used.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Characterization of the viscoelastic behaviour

Dynamic Mechanical Analyses were performed on hemp fibres. DMA is a particularly convenient way to measure the damping capacity of a material and also determine its transition temperatures. This method is also useful to observe and quantify the evolution of viscoelastic properties as a function of testing (frequency, amplitude...) and environmental (moisture, temperature...) parameters.

So, hemp fibres were submitted to tensile-tensile cyclic loading with a peak-to-peak amplitude of approximately 50 mN for different environmental and loading conditions. The main results were published in (20, 21). They showed that the damping capacity varies, as for most of the polymeric materials, with frequency and temperature but also with moisture and as a function of cumulated tensile cyclic loading. The loss factor varies from 0.15 to values below 0.01 as a function of these parameters, indicating a significant level of viscoelasticity under certain environmental conditions. A strong coupling between cyclic loading time and frequencies, moisture sorption and viscoelastic properties was also observed. Fig. 2 gives an insight of some of the collected results.

Figure 2: Normalized storage modulus (left) and loss factor (right) versus number of cycles at two solicitation frequencies (1 Hz and 0.1 Hz) at room temperature. (I and II: 2 stages of loading separated by 15 min of unloading)

An increase in the fibre's rigidity was observed with repeated tensile loading at constant amplitude. In Fig. 2, it can be clearly seen that the apparent rigidity of the fibre increases until, after 1000 cycles (1 Hz), it is 1.3 times greater than its initial value. The stiffening effect and decrease in damping capacity under cyclic tensile loading was discussed in previous papers (20-23) and was attributed to a re-orientation of cellulose microfibrils in the fibre axis. The loading rate influences also directly this stiffening phenomenon (Fig. 2). In the considered frequency range, after 1000 cycles, the storage modulus is about 1.3 times higher than the initial value for a solicitation frequency of 1 Hz while for 0.1 Hz the storage modulus is only 1.1 times higher. After a definite time of cycling, the fibre was unloaded during 15 min. It clearly comes out that the stiffness increase due to cycling is a partially reversible phenomenon. This result indicates the involvement of viscoelastic mechanisms in the stiffening phenomenon.

The strong coupling between cyclic loading and frequency, moisture sorption and viscoelastic properties makes DMA tests particularly difficult to be interpreted. Taking into account also that the harmonic tests give a complex function in terms of frequency and that the conversion of dynamic results and conclusion to static, i.e. on a time scale, is not always obvious, we choose in this work to realise also static tests.

The evolution of the fibre strain when submitted to a typical creep-recovery test is plotted in Fig.3. When loaded, the fibre exhibits both instantaneous strain and time-dependent strain. The extension is found to increase rapidly at first (during the 15 first minutes) and more slowly after. These two creep

components are classically called primary creep and secondary creep. As in many cases (7, 8, 12), the creep of elementary hemp fibres appears as a logarithmic function of time. When the load is removed, the fibre contracts, more quickly at first (during the first minutes) again. However the retraction rate after the first time of recovery is higher than for the secondary creep. During the recovery step, a small tensile load is maintained to avoid buckling of the fibre. Our results clearly show that, even after a prolonged time of retraction, a significant residual extension or permanent set remains. The instantaneous recovery, when the applied load is released, is extremely small in comparison to the initial instantaneous strain. Only a portion of the delayed strain is recovered after 3 hours. For most of the viscoelastic materials, the primary creep is considered as the time-dependent recoverable portion of the delayed strain, as the secondary creep is the portion of the total sample strain which is non-recoverable at the test conditions after removal of the load.

This time-dependent phenomena with large permanent set could affect the dimensional stability and other performance characteristics of natural fibres reinforced composites, and has to be taken into account.

Figure 3: Creep-recovery test on a single hemp fibre. Evolution of tensile load and strain as a function of time ($T=23^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1.5^{\circ}\text{C}$)

Few tens of fibres were tested in the same experimental conditions. The loading rate used for each fibre corresponds to a stress rate of $50 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. The duration of the dwell at this load level was 3 000 s. Using a logarithmic timeline, it clearly appears that three different creep behaviours can be observed. Typical behaviours are represented in Fig. 4 (extensive results are also presented in (16, 24)). Type II is truly linear as a function of the logarithm of time. Type I and Type III are strongly nonlinear. Type I is described by a concave function and Type III by a convex one. Three types of monotonic tensile behaviour were already observed for hemp fibres (23, 25-27). The origin of these

different behaviours is unknown. The hypothesis of maturity, or the position of the fibres in the stem, could be considered. Indeed, technical fibres from hemp stem are composed of primary and secondary fibres, both originating from the phloem. These two different types of bast fibres (primary and secondary fibres) found in hemp have different and independent types of development, and also have different morphological and biochemical compositions which could lead to different mechanical behaviours (28). The different creep behaviours observed in this work could result from the same origins.

Figure 4: Three types of creep behaviour observed for hemp fibres (Constant load corresponding to an initial tensile stress of 50 MPa, $T=23^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1.5^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{RH}=50\% \pm 2.5\%$). Experimental and model curves.

The identified parameters of the proposed model for each type of behaviour are listed in Tab. 1. The values of the identified axial components of the viscoelastic compliance (S_{ZZ}) and of the time constant τ_1 are respectively $1.6 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ MPa}^{-1}$ and 563 s for Type I and $2.4 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ MPa}^{-1}$ and 5.6 s for Type III. These results seem to reflect the existence of several viscoelastic mechanisms, with different time constants, which can express more or less as a function of the fibre under constant environmental conditions. The physical or macromolecular origin of these mechanisms remains to be defined. Anyway, the proposed model allows two mains release times to be balanced.

Creep curve-type	τ_1 (s)	σ_d (s)	n_{min}	n_{max}	S_{ZZ} (MPa^{-1})
1	562.9	2.2	0.79	0.37	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$
2	64.3	11.6	0.10	0.12	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$
3	5.6	3	0.10	0.71	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-5}$

Table 1: Fitted parameters for the different creep curve-types with inverse Gaussian spectral model

Creep behaviour was also investigated at different RH levels. Results are presented in Fig. 5. The time-delayed strain considerably increases with increasing RH (Fig. 5 and Tab. 2). For the considered creep time (4000 s), the time-delayed strain is of about 0.19% at 40% RH and 0.63% at

80% RH. Both primary creep and secondary creep rates also increase with RH. Between 40% and 80% RH these rates are respectively multiplied by factors 5 and 7 (Tab. 2). Humidity is clearly an activator of the viscoelastic properties of hemp fibres. This is confirmed by the parameters of the viscoelastic model which were identified at each RH level. Tab. 3 synthetises the values of the identified parameters. RH increase induces an increase in S_{ZZ} and τ_1 values. It varies respectively from $4.7 \cdot 10^{-5}$ to $1.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ MPa}^{-1}$ and from approximately 19 s to 92 s between 40% and 80% of RH. Such empirical relationship could be used to calibrate a time-humidity equivalence.

Figure 5 Successive creep/recovery tests on a same single fibre at increasing RH levels: 40, 60 and 80% RH ($T=23^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1.5^{\circ}\text{C}$). Superimposed creep curves recorded at each successive RH plateau are plotted after time re-zeroing.

RH (%)	EMC (%)	Instantaneous strain (%)	Time-delayed strain (%)	Initial primary creep strain rate 10^{-5} s^{-1}	Secondary creep strain rate 10^{-8} s^{-1}
40	8	0.21	0.19	4.1	4
60	10.5	0.17	0.39	8.7	12.5
80	15.5	0.2	0.63	20.4	29.4

Table 2: Creep properties for a single hemp fibre submitted to different dwells in RH (Constant stress: 50 MPa)

RH (%)	τ_1 (s)	σ_d (s)	S_{ZZ} (MPa^{-1})	n_{min}	n_{max}
40	19.3	3.2	$4.7 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.3	0.64
60	14.4	3.7	$9.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.21	0.53
80	92.1	2.7	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.53	0.56

Table 3: Fitted parameters for the different creep curves recorded at different RH levels for inverse Gaussian spectral model

Creep under cyclic humidity was also investigated. A RH of approximately 80% was applied for 5000 s. Then, the RH was cycled between 80 and 15% at a RH variation rate of 20%RH.min⁻¹. After five cycles, the RH was returned to its original value and maintained constant for 5000s. The RH was again cycled between 80 and 15% but for this sequence at a RH variation rate of 8%RH.min⁻¹. After five cycles, the RH was again returned to its original value and maintained constant for 5000s. A considerable acceleration in creep strain rate (5.5 10⁻⁸ s⁻¹ to 2.7 10⁻⁷ s⁻¹) is observed when the first RH cycling stage is applied. When the RH is returned to its maximal and constant value, the creep strain rate decreases to reach a value in the same order of magnitude that the initial one (3 10⁻⁸ s⁻¹). This rate remains constant during the second RH cycling stage (with the low RH rate) and during the successive RH plateau. This result clearly shows that the creep acceleration under cyclic RH is only observed for high RH rates. This result is in agreement with the work of Habberger *et al.* (10) who have observed for several hydrophilic fibres that the MCS creep occurrence is dependent on the moisture cycling rate. The time parameters of the humidity cycling must be matched to the sorption time of the sample, and therefore to the size of the fibre and of the wall thickness. For low RH rates, this match is not respected and the creep is not accelerated. This observation also supports the sorption-induced stress-gradient explanations proposed by these authors. This point is widely discussed in (16, 24).

Figure 6: Evolution of creep strain as a function of time for a single fibre submitted to two successive stages of RH cycling with a respective variation rate of 8%RH/min and 20%RH/min (Stress = 50 MPa, T = 25°C±1.5°C).

4.2 Influence of viscoelasticity on the nonlinear tensile behaviour of hemp fibres

The anisotropic viscoelastic constitutive law identified using creep tests under constant RH was implemented in a 3D model of plant fibre. The macroscopic simplified 3D model used for this study is based on a previously developed model, described in detail in (15, 29). The elementary hemp fibre is idealised as a layered, hollow, thick-walled cylinder made of an orthotropic material having a helical orientation (corresponding to the cellulose microfibril orientation). The wall is modelled as if it were a long fibre-reinforced composite material, made with a mixture of three different polymers. The wall properties are determined using a homogenisation technique. In order to take into account the variation in the cellulose microfibrils angle as a function of tensile load, a consistent approach based on kinematic and material considerations has been proposed. It assumes that the fibre is locally subjected to finite transformations which involve large rotations and small elastic-viscoelastic strains (15).

The material parameters used for FE computation are listed in Tab. 4.

Elastic parameters		Viscoelastic parameters	
E_L	75 000 MPa	β_{LT}	12.25
E_T	11 000 MPa	β_T	1.5
ν_{LT}	0.153	z_{n_c}	2.45
G_{LT}	2 520 MPa	z_{n_0}	1.9
ν_{TT}	0.2		

Table 4: Values of the model parameters used in the FE computations

Fig. 7 shows the stress-strain and apparent tangent modulus – strain curves for different strain rates from $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ to $5 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. As expected and as for all polymeric materials, the fibre response depends directly on the strain rate. Our results show that the degree of nonlinearity decreases with an increase in strain rate.

Figure 7: Computed stress-strain curves (left) and apparent tangent modulus – strain curves (right). The curves are computed for different strain rates from $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ to $5 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Results showed a significant time- humidity dependent behaviour of hemp fibres. This point is of great importance in view of their integration in composite materials. The integration of the viscoelastic behaviour of natural fibres in the predictive mechanical models of natural fibre and natural fibres reinforced plastics is definitely necessary to ensure the reliability of the designed structures, in particular for long-term applications.

The creep behaviour appears to be a logarithmic function of time with a high strain rate during the primary creep and a lower and constant one during the secondary creep. A large scattering both in time-delayed strains and behaviour was observed on a set of single fibres tested under constant climate. Three main creep behaviours were observed. A model based on anisotropic viscoelastic law and on a truncated inverse Gaussian spectrum of viscous mechanisms was shown to successfully describe all the experimentally observed behaviours.

Results also underlined that both primary and secondary creep strain rates increase with increasing moisture content. More creep is also observed in cyclic humidity conditions than in a constant environment at the high-humidity. In agreement with some observations on synthetic fibres, we showed that this accelerated creep is only observed for high moisture cycling rates. This mechanosorptive effect is consistent with sorption-induced stress-gradient explanations proposed in literature.

The anisotropic viscoelastic law identified using creep tests was implemented in a 3D fibre model. Simulations of the tensile behaviour of such plant fibres highlight the high influence of time-dependent mechanisms in their nonlinear response.

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